

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Mapping leadership characteristics - Analysis of the trends in leadership characteristics for organizations adopting remote working [SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 4

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1 Introduction

The SMART WEST project would like to provide analyses, best practices, intervention lines, tools, and devices to fully exploit the potential of agile and remote working to enhance business performance and improve worker wellbeing and enable companies to organize these models of work effectively and orderly in the mountain areas of the NODES ecosystem, including the southern regions participating in the project, as Basilicata.

From the point of view of the organizational change (Flagship project 1, Research module 4), the application of agile and remote working requires not only a review of processes, work practices and organizational structure, but also a cultural evolution and the creation of a collaboration system based on trust, flexibility, autonomy and the enhancement and improvement of employee skills. This requires renewed management practices and leadership skills.

This document reports the main results of a literature review on the main trends regarding challenges and opportunities for leadership in agile and remote working and the characteristics and skills required to entrepreneurs and managers to lead the organization in remote working contexts, and more generally, to effectively navigate in the Digital Transformation (DT) scenario.

The main findings of the literature review reside in an examination of new forms of leaderships required in digital age, with a specific focus on DT, the identification of the trends about the main challenges and opportunities for leaders in remote working setting and a systematization of the main traits and competencies required to remote leaders and managers to successfully lead their organization.

The need of creating and maintaining a competitive edge, successfully dealing with the rapid technological changes are forcing more and more organizations to embark DT. Remote work can be a part of the DT strategy and can help to deal with unexpected challenges, tapping into a distributed workforce that can quickly pivot and maintain business operations in challenging circumstances. DT encompasses multiple dimensions of an organisation, and the challenges of DT's success are not merely related to adopting new digital technology solutions. Successful DT transformation results from the correct meeting point between skills of people, mindsets and competencies and the opportunity provided by complex digital tools to increase value for stakeholders. Leaders and top managers are critical in governing organizational learning and transformation. They guide organisations through the DT journey by rethinking old structures and processes, fostering a culture of change and leading people to adopt a new mindset, knowledge, attitudes and ways of working to thrive under continuous change. Based on the results of the literature review, the report describes the notions of transactional, transformational, entrepreneurial and wise leaders which are some distinctive leadership styles to navigate an organisational transformation, denoting a leadership capacity of activating, supporting and managing the processes of an organisation's transformation. Remote work can be a part of the DT strategy and can help deal with unexpected challenges, tapping into a distributed workforce that can quickly pivot and maintain business operations in challenging circumstances.

Specifically, the literature review highlights the advantages and the risks of the agile and remote working, effectively distinguishing the perspectives of analysis and considering separately the *employees' view*, the *company view* and the *social view*. On these base, it emerges the need to define and analyse which kind of leadership styles are best suited and fitted to the agile and increasingly digitised organizational contexts. In particular, it is stressed as the profiling of the remote leader is fundamental to lead modern organisations to identify and select effectively managers capable to successfully meet the challenges and the opportunities of the new modelling of the work activities.

Accordingly, the literature review suggests a plethora of traits and key competences that leaders operating in remote setting should have. These competences range from personal to professional skills needed for leadership in agile and remote work. They can be grouped as: *Interpersonal and Relationship Competences*, including emotional intelligence, communication skills, trust & relationship-building skills, conflict management skills, inclusivity skills; *Problem-Solving and Adaptability*, including flexibility and adaptability and problem solving skills; *Professional and Technical Competences*, including technology proficiency and data literacy and trustworthiness; and *Goal Oriented Mindset and Project Management competences*, including goal-oriented mindset and team accountability, goal alignment and vision, team recognition and time and task management skills.

Certainly, the list of the reported distinguishing competences is not exhaustive and additionally may vary depending on the organization's culture, industry, and the nature of the remote work being conducted. Additionally, the list of leadership skills can fit within multiple further categories.

The realm of remote leadership continues to evolve, giving rise to several potential avenues for future research and emerging trends. In particular, a more in depth exploration of the phenomenon and its managerial and practical implications on field is required.

2 Background

In the last years it is widely recognized the great relevance to understand, identify and manage the competencies, skills and abilities required to people in terms of behaviors and actions addressing leadership in agile and remote working organizational contexts. This is linked both to the benefits of elaborating valuable suggestions for companies and organizations interested – for opportunity or need – to embrace these new emerging models and to the advantages related to the attraction, retention and growth of executive and top managers capable to face the challenges associated with the changes of working [1,2].

Despite this importance and the attention recently paid by academic and managerial studies trying to shed light on these issues by addressing the question of what kind of leadership could be fitted in the new scenarios of working, a full and shared setting of findings, insights and managerial and policy guidelines about the new styles of leadership and the required characteristics for a leader best suited the creation and the management of agile and remote working teams is still missing and results presented often in a jeopardized way [3].

This descriptive study aims to support to close these gaps in current knowledge by means of a scoping literature review. First, the concepts grounding the whole research are introduced. Then, the new leadership styles and associated characteristics to be asked by the emerging organizational contexts and work modeling are presented and specifically analyzed. Specifically, based on a literature review, this study investigates the existing knowledge about the relationships between agile and remote working and new forms of leadership. Between April and September 2023, a literature review was carried out looking for scientific publications on the notions under investigation in academic journals-databases (Web of Sciences, SCOPUS, etc.), as well as advanced managerial and policy-oriented reports. Only recent and focused articles were included in the analysis. Then, the body of the collected and selected sources was reviewed and organized for presentation in this document.

2.1 Concepts definitions

Different scholars have recently argued that the exponential development and adoption of increasingly high-performing technologies and the significant impact of the DT on the business processes have determined –

among the different effects – also the emergence of different ways of working characterised by the possibility to perform at any location and at any time [4].

While organisations of different industries were getting for the technology-driven future, the world has been unexpectedly hit by the COVID-19 pandemic. Beyond the dramatic aspects of the humanitarian crisis, it determined a breakthrough of all the economic activities. Accordingly, in order to guarantee economic survival and business continuity avoiding social contacts, companies and organisations encouraged and supported employees to work from home as much as possible. In this way, the most significant organisation and workplace design shock of our recent lifetimes was happening [5,6]. However, it is important to underline that, before the COVID-19, these ways of working were steadily growing globally across many industries and infrastructures already existed [7]: in this sense, the pandemic only accelerated these processes [2].

Consequently, the expressions “*agile working*” and “*remote working*”, as well as the related “*smart working*” and “*teleworking*”, emerged as mainstream concepts to identify and synthesize these new trends as well as the technological, organizational and human resource-related variables involved, the positive and negative consequences and finally the effects, the opportunities and the challenges both at individual, organizational and societal level.

Accordingly, a full comprehension of these new approaches and related implications for human resource management and a suitable and coherent leadership capable to serve as a guide for organizations and for existing and future leaders is fundamental for scientists as well as for practitioners involved on these fields.

2.1.1 Agile working

The notion of “agility” is traditionally related to the organizational capacity to identify new trends, opportunities and threats, to be fast, pro-active and resilient, to have change-ready mindset to keep moving, changing and adapting to the general and task environment in which operates or could operate, mainly innovating business modelling, rethinking products and services to be addressed to actual and potential customers/users, revisiting operations, exploring the value of new resources and assets and defining a new platform of commercial and non-commercial relationships [8].

In relation to work practices, different scholars have focused the perspective of the “*agile working*” and have referred to agility as “*the ability to react quickly to fragmented world market situations full of constant and unexpected changes*” [9], as the set of practices used to determine solutions using cross-functional and self-organized teams [10], as the “*summa of the adaptability, the quick response and the great execution*” [11].

Other scholars, instead, have paid attention to the perspective of the “*workforce agility*”, defined as the capacity of the employees to be “*well-trained and flexible, capable to adapt quickly and easily to new opportunities and market circumstances*” [12]. The same author also identified seven key attributes of an agile workforce, such as adaptability, flexibility, positive attitude towards development, speed, collaboration, competence and information [13]. [14] define the agile workforce as a workforce each of whom is trained to do multiple jobs in the company to which they belong, while [15], in connection to this, underline the necessity of replacing multi-level and rigid management structures with leaner and more flexible forms to better receive feedback allowing adaptation to customers requests and needs.

The effect of the adoption of agile forms on organizational human resource management practices is also a topic of the [16] stating that “*the new mission of HRM is to push people towards new frontiers by motivating them and exploiting their strengths so that required goals can be achieved*”. This implies that Human Resource managers should encourage the growth of individual talents by making them responsible for the role they play in the company, also in relation to the greater freedom in organizing and planning their activities anywhere and at any time [3].

2.1.2 Remote working

Together with the agile working, a further relevant concept introduced to analyse the new work environments and practices is remote working, often used as umbrella notion embracing other terms such as smart working [1, 17, 18, 19], teleworking, working at home, and home-based work [20, 21]. It can be considered, then, a wide-ranging concept covering any paid work performed from a distance in any place different from the physical presence in the organization where employees meet organizational objectives through ICTs at their preferred time [22,23,24].

Despite different contributions have been provided to define and operationalize it [25, 26], unfortunately remote working till now does not have a universally-accepted definition and often it is overlapped with the agile working one [27, 3, 20]. This orientation is confirmed also by [28] describing remote working as *“an agile and dynamic way of working that leads to high performance, greater productivity and better satisfaction” for organizations and employees*“.

This tendency to use the concepts interchangeably is confirmed by the analysis of the research aimed to explore the nature, the effects and the advantages and disadvantages determined by such ways of working as well as to the challenges and opportunities that will be analysed in the following sections. For simplicity purposes, in the next sections the two concepts will be used merging them in the unique wider notion of remote working.

2.1.3 Leadership

The notion of leadership is one of the most debated issues in the managerial literature. Accordingly, different definitions have been provided as well as various research streams have paid attention to different scientific and managerial aspects related to the notion of leadership, such as leadership theories [29, 30], leadership styles [31, 30], leadership traits [32, 33, 34, 35], leadership types [36], relationships among leadership, organizational performance and organizational variables [37, 38, 39], leadership and teamworking [36], leadership and innovation capacity [40].

On the base of the extensive and effective review work by [29] summarizing the main defining statements on leadership elaborated by scholars ranging more than one century of scientific research on the topics, a working and brief definition of leadership refers to an highly-complex social process of influencing a group toward the achievement of goals and directing the organization to make it more cohesive and coherent applying specific values, beliefs, technical and emotive knowledge, experiences and culture [41, 29].

Of course, the notion of leadership – as well as the related aspects cited before - has evolved according to the changing of the general and task environments in which companies and organisations operate and compete [42]. It determines that situations, contexts, new laws and regulations, information availability and use, timing, technological variables and cultural and psycho-socio dynamics heavily impact the leadership notion historically framed, aligning it in a fine tuning manner to the evolution of the economic, organizational and social scenarios [43].

2.2 Leadership and DT

DT is a crucial challenge and, at the same time, a big opportunity for businesses today [44, 45]. The need of creating and maintaining a competitive edge in a globalised market, successfully dealing with the rapid technological changes and continuing to generate value for customers and stakeholders are forcing more and more organizations to embark DT [46].

DT has a huge potential that companies recognise. The Covid-19 pandemic, the high international geopolitical instability, the socio-economic changes, and the rapid progress in digital technologies have pushed organisations to adopt digital technologies to create new or change existing business models and processes, improve productivity and support organisational structures and resources or stakeholder relationships.

Despite the exponential attention to implementing DT, the companies' digital maturity is heterogeneous. Some companies are still beginning their DT journey, while others are experiencing barriers due to significant cultural, cognitive, and economic barriers [47, 48]. Indeed, capturing value from implementing DT is not straightforward, and many organisations that have embarked on DT have not yet achieved their desired outcomes. Most organisations achieved less than one-third of the impact they expected from digital investments [49, 50]. DT fails to produce all expected results because it is often conceived merely as incorporating digital technology into all business areas and is not viewed as an organisational transformation involving the governance of managing digital technological knowledge together with other complementary knowledge assets [51].

DT encompasses multiple dimensions of an organisation, and the challenges of DT's success are not merely related to adopting new digital technology solutions but to enable the organisation to develop, absorb and manage new knowledge about deploying and exploiting digital technologies.

Successful DT results from the correct meeting point between people skills, mindsets and competencies and the opportunity provided by complex digital tools to increase value for stakeholders. Therefore, the active involvement of individuals in transforming and effectively managing the impact of continuous change on their attitudes, behaviours, and practices is crucial for DT [52].

Leaders and top managers are critical in governing organizational learning and transformation [53]. Analysing the successful cases of digital and traditional companies that have led the transformation towards digital-based business models emerges a key leadership role in determining successful organisational transformation [54, 55, 56, 57, 58]. They guide organisations through the DT journey by rethinking old structures and processes, fostering a culture of change and leading people to adopt a new mindset, knowledge, attitudes and ways of working to thrive under continuous change.

Different labels have been used in the management literature to understand the leadership styles to navigate an organisational transformation, denoting a leadership capacity of activating, supporting and managing the processes of an organisation's transformation. In particular, the notions of transactional, transformational, entrepreneurial and wise leaders can be distinguished as critical ones [59, 60, 61].

Since its conceptualisation [62], the traditional transactional leadership approach equates leaders to managers with the primary responsibility of outlining duties, assigning tasks, inspecting performance, and providing rewards or corrective actions when necessary. The transactional leadership style relies on management by exception and involves setting clear objectives and expectations for followers and monitoring their progress closely to ensure adherence to predetermined standards [63]. Transactional leaders incentivize their followers through punishments and rewards, with the main focus being attaining specific targets and objectives [60]. This type of leadership is effective in stable and predictable environments where leaders can establish explicit procedures and guidelines to facilitate goal achievement [41].

The transformational leadership has been conceived as a style designed to extend and evolve transactional leadership. It distinguishes a leader from a manager and points out leadership's relevance to being charismatic and able to inspire and motivate followers to be loyal and committed to their vision. [64] argue the importance of the transformational leader's behaviour and how it influences their followers, encompassing four key components known as the four "I"s. These components include idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration.

Idealized influence refers to a leader's ability to act as a role model and earn the trust and respect of their followers. Leaders must possess the right characteristics and communicate the organization's values and mission. Inspirational motivation involves setting a compelling vision that motivates employees to participate in achieving it. Leaders should also demonstrate optimism to boost their confidence and enthusiasm. Intellectual stimulation encourages employees to think creatively and innovatively and find unique solutions to problems. Leaders may also challenge employees to discover opportunities for optimization independently [65]. Finally, individualized consideration involves providing tailored support and guidance to meet each employee's unique needs and abilities. Leaders act as mentors to promote individual growth and development.

The transformational leadership concept enhances transactional leadership by proactively anticipating and monitoring errors to minimize them. Transformational leaders consider mistakes as opportunities for learning and development rather than criticizing or punishing employees for them [64]. They perceive mistakes as a chance to optimize and improve future outcomes. Empirical research has demonstrated that transformational leadership leads to enhanced organizational learning and innovation, resulting in improved business performance [66].

While transformational leadership has significantly developed from traditional leadership, entrepreneurial skills are highly sought in new and established companies, especially in dynamic business environments due to increasing global competition [67]. So, entrepreneurial leadership emphasizes innovativeness, risk-taking, proactiveness, autonomy, and competitive aggressiveness for individuals and companies to increase market adaptability, performance, and survivability. According to [67], team-oriented and value-based leadership principles facilitate entrepreneurial leadership, allowing leaders to inspire and guide their employees toward a shared vision of the future.

The authors formulated two dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership based on transformational leadership principles, which include future scenario formulation and implementation by personnel. An entrepreneurial leader must balance ambitious visions with the team's abilities and create challenges that push the team's limits but do not overtax them. They are responsible for formulating a persistent vision and building trust to realize it while anticipating and eliminating internal and external barriers and involving key stakeholders to facilitate its achievement. Additionally, an entrepreneurial leader must inspire and commit to achieving the vision through team-building skills and efficient use of limited resources. These two dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership are linked and cumulative, as they require the right people and a shared vision to be successful. Entrepreneurial leadership is considered suited to dynamic and uncertain environments. According to [68], entrepreneurial leaders are characterized by their willingness to take risks, identify and pursue new opportunities, and create value for their organizations. This leadership style requires leaders to be creative, innovative, and adaptable, with a high tolerance for ambiguity and uncertainty. Entrepreneurial leaders can create new markets, products, and services and generate growth and value for their organisations [68].

In the last years, with the emergence of new technologies and the need to address sustainability issues, the fundamental importance of leadership for a moral compass to guide companies in decision-making processes has emerged. As [69] noted, the digital era requires practical and ethical leaders with a clear purpose and values to guide their actions. Accordingly, wise leadership emerged as a conceptualization to consider the moral compass in today's digital world [70, 71], as an approach empowering leaders to gain wisdom.

The significance of discussing wise companies emerged from acknowledging that navigating transformation in today's complex business landscape is not enough to be a knowledge-creating company. But together with acquiring, generating and applying knowledge to support organisational growth, leaders must strive to be idealistic-pragmatic, promoting wisdom as a new form of knowledge [72]. Wise companies understand the importance of wise individuals as they drive innovation and create and practice knowledge. This approach

points out the role of leaders in navigating complex and rapidly-changing landscape of DT by ensuring that their decisions align with the values and purpose of their organisations. A wise leader should prioritise the common good by creating social and economic value while balancing attention to detail and larger goals. Wise leaders cultivate practical wisdom, and act as informed decision-makers [72]. When making choices, they must weigh factors such as changing realities, time sensitivity, and both small-scale and broad perspectives. They aim for what is best for society and the company and cultivate a sustainable approach, and they must also be able to make informed decisions in complex contexts and drive DT and innovation throughout the organisation.

The above four leadership styles highlight the importance of different leadership dimensions. While transactional leadership focuses on rewarding followers for meeting pre-defined goals, transformational leadership emphasises inspiration, motivation, and growth; entrepreneurial leadership, on the other hand, features innovation and risk-taking in dynamic and uncertain environments; and finally, wise leadership adds a moral compass to the mix, emphasizing the need for leaders to gain wisdom and align their decisions with the values and purpose of their organisations.

In the current digital era, leaders are responsible for fostering a corporate culture that supports the development of digital technological knowledge and encourages continuous organisational change, both in terms of mindset and approach, to establish new businesses or enhance existing ones by prioritizing and utilising digital technologies to continuously improve and enhance the creation of value for the company.

Furthermore, these leaders must also be familiar with the evolving setting of remote working.

Remote work introduces a shift in leadership paradigms. Transformative leaders must encourage trust and autonomy among their remote workers while also fostering a sense of belonging and sharing of organizational goals.

In the broader context of continuous organizational change, remote work can act as a catalyst for improving flexibility and adaptability. Remote work can be a part of the DT strategy and can help deal with unexpected challenges, tapping into a distributed workforce that can quickly pivot and maintain business operations in challenging circumstances.

3. Challenges and opportunities for leadership in remote working

A rather wide literature has highlighted, in the last years, the advantages and the risks of the remote working [2, 5, 24, 73]. Understanding and deeply analyzing these aspects represent a fundamental propedeutic conditions to try to identify and delineate challenges and opportunities for leadership.

In order to carry on a rigorous analysis of these multifaceted issues, following the main framing used by [73], it could be useful and important to distinguish the perspectives of analysis, considering separately the *employees' view*, the *company view* and the *social view*. In fact, although very interconnected, the same phenomena may determine different perceptions and usefulness.

According to an *employees' view*, in terms of advantages, well-being is identified as the main positive effect [74, 75], thanks to the greater flexibility and a better balance between private and professional life enabling higher level of productivity and efficiency [28, 8, 19, 76, 77]. On these basis, empirical studies have found favorable outcomes of agile and remote working in specific elements such job performance, job satisfaction, work-life balance [78], reduced rates of stress and better productivity [79, 80], time of commuting, costs savings related to daily transport, reduced turnover intentions [81, 82, 83, 84] till to reach a better employees' quality of life and happiness [85].

Always in this vein, [86] highlights effectively the role of the technological support in activating these positive dynamics, while [87] underlines the possibility to increase job opportunities for women and people with disabilities.

However, also negative consequences have been mapped, such as isolation, loneliness and burnout [88] and forms of technostress related to multitasking, permanent connectivity, anxiety about the possible shrinking of career prospects owing to reduced visibility [89], overload of information [90, 91] capable to determine increasing demotivation [24, 78], work-family struggles [22] till to quite-quitting behaviours and workforce turnover.

According to a *company view*, advantages are traced in contributing to the organizational commitment [92, 93], in reducing the rate of absenteeism, in enhancing the process of standardization of procedures [94], in influencing the reputation and the corporate image due to the “*green-oriented*” behaviours related to reduction of traffic and daily transports, pollution, and use of energy sources within the workplaces [95]. Moreover, companies may have access to specialized expertise, regardless of the team members’ location, which allows companies to find more creative solutions [96].

At the same time, different scholars [5, 73, 2] highlight that also potential disadvantages emerge, as negative impact on the organizational culture and values [24, 97, 98], difficulties in managing conflicts, team building, team working and engagement [99, 100, 101], difficulties of monitoring and coaching remote workers and preserving experiential knowledge [22], possibilities of decreasing mutual trust and company loyalty due to the physical absence from the company [21], risks for the IT security of the company [73].

Finally, according to a social view, reduction of pollution and reduction of time for transportation and commuting are identified as the main environmental and social benefits. Also upgrading of the interest and the attractive capacity of the rural areas and the reduction of the cities’ congestion can be considered further elements of advantages [73]. At the same time, exacerbation of the digital divide between countries, and above all between organizations and employees accessing and using these opportunities and traditional and not-ready ones can be identified as further dysfunctionalities.

On these base, in the last times, it strongly emerges the need to define and analyse which kind of leadership styles are best suited and fitted to the agile and increasingly digitised organizational contexts. In particular, the profiling of the remote leader is fundamental to lead modern organisations to identify and select effectively managers capable to successfully meet the challenges and the opportunities of the new modelling of the work activities.

4 Leadership in Remote Work Settings: key characteristics and competences

Identifying the traits and competences needed for leadership in remote work settings is crucial for generating suggestions for organizations adopting these modes of working and uncovers some potential needs of leaders who might face the challenges and opportunities of “digital revolution”. Recently, a few scholars have explored the topic of leadership in the context of remote work. The majority of the studies on leadership in remote working have been produced in last two years, highlighting a growing interest in the subject, motivated also by the spread of the DT process in organizations and the effects produced by the pandemic. Studies on leadership in remote working are still scarce, the knowledge of this topic is in an early stage of development [102, 103, 104, 105, 106, 107, 108]. There is not a theory specific to such leadership and it is unclear whether the current knowledge on leadership can be applied to e-leadership [5].

To date, there is not a clear consensus on the best leadership style or the characteristics of a leader managing remote working teams. Scholars have explored suitable leadership in such contexts, but common conclusions are still lacking [94,3].

In their work [109] identify several emerging key leadership characteristics in remote work settings. Drawing on the results of a narrative literature review on leading virtual teams, the scholars point out which behaviours and traits a good virtual leader should have. According to the scholars a leader operating in remote working “should build trust, be empathetic and be open to diverse groups (starting with the tolerance for several time zones). At the same time, it is her or his responsibility to create a culture of “belonging” and ‘being there for one another’, ‘caring’, ‘listening’ and empathy. What is required here is the ability to communicate and to have emotional intelligence. A virtual leader is always available, approachable, addressable, and open. She or he demands by promoting an open mindset, because she or he is a good example herself or himself” (p. 7). Additionally, [109] underscore that leading team in remote working requires building trust and a culture of collaboration and support among team members. According to the authors, leaders should manage conflicts and identify frustration in the team early on as well as organize regular meetings, either formal or informal, where team members can socialize.

The crucial importance of meeting all remote workers, also in person if possible, and enhancing social interactions to reduce misunderstanding and feelings of loneliness typically experienced by remote workers, have been addressed by several authors [e.g., 110, 111, 112].

Other authors have analysed the style to build effective interactions and relationships in remote working.

According to some authors [e.g., 113, 114], remote leaders should adopt a task oriented leadership style to build effective and trusted relationships and job satisfaction in teams. They should promote among workers an intensive task-related orientation at a distance, then facilitate face-to-face social opportunities, and finally allow workers return to remote locations to continue work. There are some empirical evidences that a task-oriented leadership style would produce more communication satisfaction, job satisfaction and telecommuter organisational commitment than relational-oriented leadership.

However, these findings contrast with other studies [e.g., 110, 115, 116] pointing out the relevance of relationship-oriented leadership. According to these studies, leaders should be relationships-oriented as stronger relationships support a more developed mutual understanding, because the messages exchanged are more frequent and briefer and characterized by a more proactive focus on the problems or challenges faced by the work. This is particularly important considering the fact that challenges and conflicts are increasingly difficult to resolve in remote communities compared to traditional contexts [110]. In remote setting increased technological frustrations, barriers to performance, loss of interest, and cultural differences can undermine problem solving process. Remote leaders must adopt a proactive role and establish rules and procedures to resolve problems that arise [e.g., 106].

The crucial importance of relationships, meetings, building trust, effective communication is widely highlighted also by [5]. These latter scholars, investigating tele-working and e-leadership, underline that e-leaders must develop technical competencies to monitor, coordinate, and align work through technology-supported structures, reducing barriers. They must be expert with latest ICTs and create awareness for teleworking. Remote leaders should stay updated on technological advancements, seek out technological solutions, and remain informed about recent developments in their areas of expertise [e.g., 94, 106, 116].

As remote environments can influence workers' behaviors, emotions, thoughts, and performance, according to [5], e-leaders must reduce physical and psychological distances, by being close to employees, creating trust through interrelationship and avoiding to organize fragmented tasks. They should develop intercultural competences to communicate adequately with team members and build effective, autonomous,

interdependent and committed virtual teams. The scholars remark the importance of developing trust in employees' relationships, allowing greater exchange of ideas, encouraging information flow, generating creative solutions and boosting employees' work engagement.

Moreover, [5] in their study, confirm the importance of shared leadership. Shared leadership encourages team members to take responsibility for their work and the project, promoting identification within the team and initiating action flows for goal achievement.

Analogously, [98] states that "beyond technical and business skills, leadership must acquire specialized aptitudes for coaching, adaptability, career guidance, communicating, interpersonal relationships, and developing cultural sensitivity" (p. 3). Remote leaders must also recognize and cultivate talent that can solve problems, network with their peers, and direct their own projects. Additionally, an essential role of leadership is building personal relationships as this may be the only connection workers have with the organization and how they form their impression of it. Remote working lacks physical interaction. Therefore, leaders have to guarantee that remote employees feel a part of work's social connectedness, by arranging proper team events and promoting new communication etiquette. This is particularly important considering that workforce has varying personalities from multicultural backgrounds that need a common ethos and collaboration.

The importance of nourishing right communication by leaders in remote setting, has been addressed also by [24]. These scholars analyze in depth the difficulties and challenges of communication that remote workers have daily to face and propose a leadership model for workers' induction. The model highlights that leaders must concentrate on building relationships among employees and enhancing their skills to overcome the numerous communication problems in the absence of physical proximity.

Some scholars [e.g., 94, 117] used the term "e-communication" to describe the ability of leaders to communicate clearly, prevent mistakes and misunderstandings, and not harm workers' productivity through communications technologies.

The literature review suggests three main features characterizing an effective leader's communication in remote working. i.e. *i)* a clear setting goals and expectations- leaders should communicate clear goals and objectives; this helps clearly define the roles and responsibilities within the team, align behaviours and to develop identification-based trust [e.g., 117, 118]; *ii)* the existence of communication norms - remote leaders must be aware of communicational changes in the remote setting and should respond to these changes by establishing and periodically revisiting communication norms [e.g., 94], and *iii)* an explicit communicate intent - remote leaders should communicate intent by clarifying expectations, asking questions and clearly explaining perspectives [119].

In a recent work [3], through a scoping literature review of 54 relevant studies, have identified leadership qualities, potential skills, and how varied leadership approaches can foster fitting innovative work behaviors, in agile and remote work settings.

Table 1 reports the forms of leadership directly associated with remote/agile working identified by the scholars.

Leadership style	Main characteristics
Directive Leadership	Ability to organise and manage work, defining the roles of each employee. Power to exercise control over the initiating structure model.
Catalyst Leadership	Ability to lead change by involving Human Resource, creating a climate of trust and participation.
Resonant Leadership	Ability to spread enthusiasm and trust. It is intended as a real contagion of emotions.
Servant Leadership	Ability to influence others by acting as a guide, with the aim of promoting team success rather than personal success, taking into account the employee's well-being and creating a relationship of mutual trust with human resources.
Transformational Leadership	Ability to encourage human resources to achieve company objectives, in an agile work context.
Authentic Leadership	Creating authentic and sincere relationships with the group.
E-leadership / Leadership 4.0	Ability to guide human resources using technological supports.
Distributed Leadership	Possession of direction and management skills.
Shared Leadership	Ability to fully share one's role as leader, one's powers, and one's commitments, with the teams.

Table 1. Styles of leadership discussed in relation to remote or agile working environments and their main characteristics (Source: [3])

Directive leadership is a style of leadership in which the leader gives orders on how work is to be done. This style of leadership can be advantageous in the early phase of a change process, as it allows the leader to provide clear guidance to the team. However, directive leadership can be problematic in the long term. Leading teams with directive style can generate decreased autonomy and responsibility for employees. This, in turn, can generate an environment that is hostile to change and can lead to technostress, anxiety, and a toxic organizational climate.

Catalyst leadership is a style of leadership in which the leader shares his/her vision of change with the team and inspires them to use their skills to achieve it. The catalyst leadership culture is characterized by high levels of participation, empowerment, and teamwork. A catalyst leader can successfully provide guidance in flexible contexts, such as remote work.

Resonant leadership is a style of leadership that seeks to motivate and inspire team members by creating a positive and engaging work environment. Resonant leader, through his/her empathy, is able to connect with workers on an emotional level, building trust and empathy, activate a collective sense-making and foster a strong shared meaning to change. Resonant leadership is particularly effective in agile and remote working settings, where it can help build a sense of community and collaboration.

Servant leadership is a leadership style in which leader is always mindful of the needs of their team members. Servant leaders listen to their employees and understand their needs and emotions. They are humble and altruistic, and they are always willing to help their team grow and develop. Servant leadership is considered an ideal leadership style for agile organizations, where change is constant and flexibility is required., as it promotes collaboration, empowerment, and continuous learning and employee commitment to change.

Transformational leadership is a style of leadership that inspires and motivates employees to work towards the company's goals by giving them feedback and recognition. It is especially effective in flexible work settings, such as remote working, where employees have more autonomy and responsibility over their tasks, the traditional boundaries of time and space are overcome.

Authentic leadership is a style of leadership which emphasizes the originality and authenticity of the relationships among people, that are essential to achieve organizational goals. Authentic leaders are particularly suitable in the context of agile working as they can foster a climate of trust, authentic relationships, collaboration and mutual exchange.

E-leadership is a style of leadership that aims to simplify the working conditions and motivate the employees to achieve the goals. E-leaders encourage employees to develop the skills and abilities that are needed for virtual and remote working environments. E-leadership was identified as the most suitable form of leadership in flexible work contexts.

Distributed leadership is a style of leadership that involves everyone who has management and direction skills. It is similar to shared leadership, which is a way of leading that is common in agile working. Shared leadership means that there is no single leader in a remote working setting, but rather a group of people who share the leadership roles and responsibilities.

Summarizing the findings of their scoping review, [3] identify some main characteristics of a leader in a remote/agile working environment. Leaders should possess emotional intelligence, which encompasses trust, empathy, and humanity. This helps in building strong relationships and understanding the needs of team members. They should be able to build strong relationships, understand the needs of team members, inspire and motivating their employees, building and planning future activities and organizational strategies always keeping the team's attention at the forefront. Leaders should also prioritize the team and share leadership roles and powers, creating a collaborative and participatory environment. Furthermore, according to the authors, the leader in a remote/agile working environment should have the following attributes: vision, inspiration, self-awareness, ability to create relationships, aptitude for continuous learning, ability to perform tasks, innovation, and ethics.

The review of management literature shows that to date the research on the leadership in remote settings is still limited, but also wide-ranging and promising. The researchers in their studies have examined one or more traits and competences characterizing leaders and their leading action in remote setting. The developed analysis of management literature on leaderships characteristics in remote working, suggest some key competences that leaders operating in such a context should have. They can be grouped as showed in Figure 1 and described in the following.

Certainly, the list of the reported distinguishing competences is not exhaustive and additionally may vary depending on the organization's culture, industry, and the nature of the remote work being conducted.

Figure 1. Leadership competences in remote setting (Source: own elaboration)

Interpersonal and Relationship Competences

Emotional intelligence: Virtual team leaders need emotional intelligence skills, such as self-awareness, i.e. the ability to understand the effects of the leader's behavior on team members; self-regulation, i.e. Being able to manage our own emotions, motivation, empathy, social skills, i.e. genuinely caring for and respect others, and communication, to understand the effects of their behavior on team members, promote knowledge exchange and honest communication, and support problem-solving. Leaders must be able to understand and empathize with their team members' unique challenges and needs in a remote work environment. They have to motivate and provide autonomy to employees in order to counteract monotony and enhance job satisfaction.

Communication Skills: Effective remote leaders should be able to communicate clearly, frequently, and transparently, using a variety of media and channels. They should also be able to utilize technology for coordination, facilitate virtual meetings, resolve conflicts, and provide feedback and recognition. In this regard, Leaders could implement three leadership strategies such as i) setting goals and expectations- remote leaders should clearly communicate the goals, roles, responsibilities and expectations within the organisation and encourage team members to describe personal objectives for successful outcomes; ii) establishing communication norms -remote leaders should introduce novel methods for communicating that reflect facial feedback in the online context, as well as communicate with followers clearly and provide information regarding the etiquette for communicating online, iii) communicating intent - remote leaders should often communicate intent with employees by clarifying expectations, asking questions and clearly explaining perspectives. Miscommunication is the Achilles heel of even the best management teams. Practice shows that remote workers are twice as likely as in-office employees to feel misunderstood or unappreciated at work. Therefore, cultivating effective communication is crucial for remote leader.

Trust & Relationship-building skills. Without physical proximity, building trust with teams can be challenging. To overcome this, remote leaders should be open and truthful. They should foster collaboration, trust, and engagement among team members. They should manage conflicts and identify frustration in the team early on as well as organize regular meetings, either formal or informal, where team members can socialize. also in person if possible, to enhance social interactions and to reduce misunderstanding and feelings of loneliness. In this regard, leaders should use richer media such as face-to-face meetings, telephone, and virtual conferencing when appropriate.

Moreover, leaders should develop a balance between relationship-oriented and task-based leadership approach when managing employees.

Conflict management skills: Remote leaders should take the initiative to manage conflict by discussing problems and issues with employees, especially in the face of technical frustration. They should address conflicts within the team promptly and constructively, finding mutually beneficial solutions. Leaders should prevent unfruitful conflicts by setting clear expectations and boundaries. They also need to keep abreast of modern developments in technology so that employees can be empowered with the resources they need to solve problems.

Inclusivity skills: Remote leaders should be aware of the potential biases and barriers that may affect team members from different backgrounds, cultures, and identities, and strive to create an inclusive and diverse work environment that values and respects everyone's contributions and perspectives. Leaders should be able to create a workplace where everyone, regardless of background, feels valued and respected. They should also be able to address issues of social isolation, burnout, and well-being that may arise in remote work settings.

Problem-Solving and Adaptability

Flexibility and Adaptability: Leaders of virtual teams should be competent, self-confident, visionary, and supportive, but also flexible, agile, and able to cope with change, complexity, and setbacks. They need to be able to adjust their leadership style and communication strategies to the needs and preferences of different team members and contexts. Leaders must be open to new ideas and ways of working flexible and adaptable to changing circumstances, as remote work environments can be unpredictable.

Problem solving skills: Remote leaders should be able to identify problems and resolve them effectively, even if without face-to-face communication. Troubleshooting in a remote environment requires early warning systems for potential problems and quick corrective actions. This requires leaders to be constantly vigilant and have a deep understanding of the team's weaknesses and potential obstacles.

Professional and Technical Competences

Technology proficiency and data literacy: Leaders of virtual teams should be familiar with the tools and platforms used for remote work, such as video conferencing, project management, and data analytics, etc. and be able to leverage them for better performance and innovation.

They should be able, either directly or with the aid of technology specialists, to ensure the use of adopted ICTs with other ICTs and traditional communication methods. They should take an ongoing approach to improving their technical skills though address the desire for speed and customization in a virtual workplace as well as they should be able to protect the privacy and security of team members' data and information.

Trustworthiness: Remote leaders must be trustworthy and reliable, as they are often not physically present to oversee their team's work. In remote working setting, a sense of trust in the leader with regard to honesty, consistency, follow-through, fairness, and general integrity, is required.

Goal oriented mindset and PM competences

Goal-oriented mindset and team accountability: Leaders must be able to set clear goals and expectations for their team members, and hold them accountable for meeting those goals. Remote leaders should ensure that workers in virtual teams are held accountable for participating and contributing. They have to be able to balance the needs of their team members with the needs of the organization, and be able to manage performance and productivity.

Goal Alignment and Vision: Remote leaders should constantly ensure that team members understand the organization's goals and vision and that individual and team objectives are aligned with the broader mission. For this purpose, it is important to inspire and motivate remote team members to work toward common goals, inspire and influence workers to translate vision into action, and create positive organizational change, as well as to build compelling shared vision among all leaders.

Team recognition: Remote leaders should make sure that virtual team members get as much opportunity for recognition, rewards, development, and advancement as “not remote” team members.

Time and Task Management skills: Remote leaders must effectively prioritize tasks and manage workloads, help team members manage their time and tasks, and ensure deadlines are met and projects are on track. This requires clear and cooperative communication with the team so that everyone understands what needs to be done, when it needs to be done and by whom.

5 Final remarks and Future Outlook for Remote Leadership

There are important differences between traditional work arrangements and remote work, that encompass also the ways of leading employees and the entire organization. The physical separation between remote leaders and team members gives rise to several challenges to deal with, that require knowledge, skills, abilities, personal characteristics and other ‘worker-based’ factors which may significantly differ from those identified for traditional leaders. Leading workers remotely is a delicate balance.

To date the research on the leadership in remote settings is still limited and is in the early stage of development [3, 103]. There is a huge need to conduct studies that rigorously examine leadership in remote working and the reasons for success and even for the failures [5].

Acquiring a more comprehensive understanding of the individual success factors or leadership characteristics traits, values, beliefs, attitudes and behaviours, defining the remote leadership role can support organisations in avoiding a lack of direction and purpose, absence of motivation and organisational commitment, and scepticism towards leader’s decisions and practice [120, 121, 122].

Drawing on the results of a literature review, this report analyses the challenges and opportunities of remote work for leadership and provides a comprehensive overview of trends in leadership characteristics for organizations adopting remote working.

In particular, it has been highlighted the advantages and the risks of the remote working, effectively distinguishing – according to [73] - the perspectives of analysis and considering separately the *employees’ view*, the *company view* and the *social view*. On these basis, it has emerged the need to define and analyse which kind of leadership styles are best suited and fitted to the agile and increasingly digitised organizational contexts. In particular, it has been stressed as the profiling of the agile leader is fundamental to lead modern organisations to identify and select effectively managers capable to successfully meet the challenges and the opportunities of the new modelling of the work activities [123].

About the leadership characteristics the literature suggests a set of skills that range from personal to professional skills needed for leadership in agile and remote work, i.e., emotional intelligence, competence and adaptability skills, communication skills, problem-solving skills, trust and relationship-building skills, technology skills and data literacy, inclusivity skills, trustworthiness, goal-oriented mindset. The list is not exhaustive and could be further refined through the analysis of case studies and the development of research on field. Additionally, the list of leadership skills is not exhaustive and many competencies can fit within multiple categories.

The landscape of remote leadership continues to evolve and several potential future research directions and trends related to remote leadership is arising, and, among them *i)* the effective leadership strategies for organizations that adopt hybrid work models, *ii)* specific digital leadership competencies required for remote leaders, *iii)* the mental health and well-being of remote leaders and their teams, *iv)* the development of training programs and resources for leaders to enhance their skills in managing remote teams effectively, *v)* strategies and best practices can leaders use to effectively manage and lead agile teams, *vi)* potential enabling or hampering factors influencing the adoption of new styles of leadership and organisational change, etc. The field of research is still wide open [124, 125].

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